

HYDROTHERMAL CONVERSION OF ORGANOSOLV LIGNIN INTO PHENOLS BY USING NICKEL RANEY CATALYST

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ABSTRACT: The use of lignocellulosic biomass to obtain fuels and chemicals produces a large amount of lignin as byproduct. Lignin valorization into chemicals needs efficient conversion process to be developed. In this work hydrocracking of organosolv lignin was performed by using Nickel Raney catalyst. Organosolv lignin was obtained from the pretreatment of eucalyptus wood at 170° C for 1h by using 1/100/100 (w/v/v) ratios biomass/oxalic acid solution (0.4% w/w)/1-butanol. The obtained organic phase of lignin in 1-butanol was used in hydrogenation tests. The conversion of lignin was carried out with a batch reactor equipped with a 0.3 l vessel with adjustable internal stirrer and heat control. The reactor was pressurized at 5 bar with hydrogen at room temperature, then the temperature was raised to 250°C and kept for 30 min. During the tests CO_x and C₁-C₃ hydrocarbons were produced at low percentage, they were quantified by CG in the stream flowing from the batch reactor when it was depressurized at room conditions. The liquid phase was analyzed by GC-MS to determine low molecular weight fragments; GPC (Gel Permeation Chromatography) was used to determine molecular size distribution before and after the hydrogenation.

Keywords: lignin, catalytic conversion, hydrogen.

1 INTRODUCTION

Lignocellulosic biomass is a sustainable source of fuels and chemicals and the conversion of the carbohydrate fraction to biofuels is a solid reality, however the research to convert lignin into high value products has yet to mature [1].

Lignin is a complex three-dimensional amorphous polymer consisting of methoxylated phenylpropanoid units of various types and its structure and composition is dependent on the plant source [2]. Due to the recalcitrance of lignin to be degraded, it is typically a waste that is combusted to produce heat and power. On the other hand, lignin is the most abundant renewable source composed of aromatic units in nature and it is worth to find sustainable way to use it as feedstock to produce intermediates of chemical industry of high value fuels.

Depolymerization of lignin strategies with new catalysts has now attracted ever-increasing attention. There are several depolymerization strategies, such as: acid/base catalyzed depolymerization/hydrolysis, pyrolysis, hydrotreating, chemical oxidation/reduction, liquid-phase reforming, gasification, and biodegradation/biochemical transformation [1,3]. Metal catalysts such as Ni/Al alloy [4], supported metal catalysts such as Pt/alumina, Pd/C, Ru/C, NiMo/Al₂O₃, Ni/SiO₂, S₂O₈-KNO₃/TiO₂ [5-11] were employed in the presence of hydrogen to convert lignin into monomers. Struven and Meier [11] tested Nickel Raney catalyst in aqueous media at high temperature and pressure under H₂ atmosphere to produce selectively highly reactive phenol and its para- or ortho-alkylated derivatives in high yields.

In this work organosolv lignin thermal hydrocracking was performed in alcoholic media under hydrogen atmosphere by using Nickel-Raney catalyst. A mild condition of temperature and pressure was used in view of a better economic sustainability of the process.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Raw material

The organosolv lignin was obtained by grinded eucalyptus treated with 1-butanol and oxalic acid at temperature of 170° C e for 60 minutes.

Preparative work was carried out in 300 mL Parr® Reactor loaded with 5 g of eucalyptus dry matter, 50 mL of 1-butanol and 50 mL of oxalic acid solution 0.167 M, under stirring condition of 400 rpm.

Obtained slurry was filtered and the cellulose fraction was washed with water and then with ethanol. Washing ethanol was recovered and added to organic fraction containing lignin. The dry matter of organic fraction (2.1% w/w) was determined keeping sample at 60 °C overnight. All used reagents were of pure grade.

2.2 Hydrothermal conversion

Tests were performed by using 300 mL Parr® Reactor loaded with 30 g of organosolv lignin solution added with 10 g 1-butanol containing Nickel Raney catalyst provided by Sigma (about 10% w/w of alcoholic solution). After swiping with H₂ to remove air, the reactor was pressurized at 5.5 bar with H₂ at room temperature.

In the experimental runs two parameters were changed: temperature, in the range 220 - 280 °C and time, in the range 30 - 90 minutes.

At the runs end, the reactor was cooled down, solution and gases were recovered and analyzed.

2.3 Analytical Methods

Lignin solution was analyzed by HPLC (Agilent 1100 series) with GPC column SUPELCO TSKgel-G4000HHR, TSKgel-G3000HHR and TSKgel-G2500HHR to determine molecular weights and GC-MS (Agilent 6890N equipped with MSD5975B) with Agilent 5MS 30m to determine molecules produced after hydrocracking. Molecules amount was obtained by using Guaiacol as internal standard. Gases, produced during experimental runs, were analyzed by microGC Agilent 3000 series with PLOTQ and Molsieve columns.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Organosolv lignin and organic solution obtained after hydrocracking were analyzed by HPLC to determine the obtained fragments at different molecular weights. Chromatogram of organosolv lignin (chromatogram *a* in Figure 1), according used standards, shows molecular

weights under 3400 dalton.

Analysis of organic solution after test made at 280 °C and 90 min (chromatogram *b* in Figure 1) shows a molecular weight, according used standards, under 1000 dalton with main peaks under 400 dalton witnessing the almost total conversion of lignin to monomers. Chromatograms at different wavelengths (220.4; 273.4; 254.4 and 320.4 nm) were performed with similar results.

Figure 1: Chromatograms at wavelength of 214.4 nm by HPLC with GPC column before (a) and after hydrocracking (b).

Thermal hydrocracking of organosolv lignin, catalyzed by Nickel-Raney, converts lignin and part of the solvent in monomers and gases. The 1-Butanol, used as solvent, has a critical pressure of 44 ± 1 bar and a critical temperature of 289 ± 2 °C [12]; all tests were performed under critical temperature and over critical pressure (tests at 280 °C has a pressure over 100 bar) so they are all in sub-critical conditions. Residence time and temperature of reaction influenced the amount of produced gases. The increasing of the residence time increases the amount of gases produced as shown in Figure 2 where is reported the produced gases versus the percent in weight of total organic solution in the reactor converted in gas (Figures 2 and 3).

Figure 2: Amount of gases produced in tests at 280 °C with 30 min and 90 min of resident time.

The increasing of temperature of reaction increases the amount of gases produced also (Fig. 3). Consumption of solvent is critical in more severe experimental conditions as shown by the large amount of solution converted in gases (at 280 °C and 90 min of residence time about 50% in weight of organic solution in reactor is converted in gases).

Residence time and temperature of reaction also influences monomers produced as shown in Table I where we are reported the most abundant molecules detected in the organic phase, after the hydrocracking, in molarity.

Figure 3: Amount of gases produced in tests at 220 °C, 250 °C and 280 °C.

Table I: Most abundant molecules produced after hydrocracking (GC-MS analysis).

	220 °C 30 min. (M)	220 °C 90 min. (M)	280 °C 30 min. (M)	280 °C 90 min. (M)
p-Cresol	0.016	0.016	0	0.099
p-Ethylguaiacol	0.007	0.011	0.087	0.108
Phenol, 2-methoxy-4-propyl	0.010	0.026	0	0
2,3,5-Trimethoxytoluene	0.008	0.016	0.204	0.263
Guaiacol	0	0	0.004	0.010
Cresol	0	0	0.042	0
Phenol, 3,4-dimethoxy	0	0	0.027	0
Syringol	0	0	0	0.051
p-Propylguaiacol	0	0	0.046	0.074
Vanillic acid	0	0	0	0.108
Total	0.042	0.069	0.411	0.714

The amount of the produced molecules increases with the increasing of residence time and temperature. The severity of the reaction also determines the type of produced molecules: vanillic acid, for example, is only produced at 280 °C and 90 min of resident time.

The optimization of the reaction parameters is therefore subordinated to the minimization of the production of gases and, above all, to the target molecules whose production should be maximized.

4 CONCLUSION

Thermal treatment of organosolv lignin with hydrogen and Nickel Raney catalyst in subcritical condition of 1-butanol solvent depolymerises the lignin in various oxygenated monomers. The hydrogenation and cracking reactions also involve the solvent and its consuming increases with the increasing of temperature and contact time.

A careful optimization of the treatment conditions is required to maximize the yield of target molecules and to minimize solvent consuming.

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